

Enhancing Nurse Knowledge Regarding Incontinence to Prevent Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries

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Background

- Prolonged incontinence exposure leads to a condition known as incontinence associated dermatitis (IAD)
- Prevalence of IAD in the hospital varies from 15%-95% and is a risk factor for hospital acquired pressure injuries (HAPI)
- HAPI's increase hospital cost, nurse workload, and tarnish facilities reputation to provide quality care

Problem Statement

The rise in patients with incontinence and the increase in HAPIs with an incontinent component indicated the need for IAD education

Purpose

Provide nurses targeted education to enhance nurse knowledge on the cause, recognition, and treatment of IAD to decrease HAPI development

Methods

- Administer pre-test for two weeks on unit
 - Ghent Global IAD Categorization tool (GLOBAID)
 - Knowledge Instrument on Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis for Clinicians (KNOW-IAD)
- Provide education session during shift
- Administer post-test
- Gather unit NDNQI prevalence study and monthly HAPI data 2020-2022
- Analyze data to assess if education increased IAD knowledge and decreased HAPIs

Knowledge Score Results

The Chi-square results were significant, suggesting that the frequency of correct responses to the GLOBAID & KNOW-IAD education are related to one another

Interpretation

- IAD Knowledge Results
 - GLOBAID percentage of correct responses increased significantly ($p < .001$)
 - KNOW-IAD percentage of correct responses increased significantly ($p < .001$)
- HAPI Results
 - Monthly HAPI rate of 0 in 4 of the 5 months post-implementation
 - NDNQI reported data remained at 0

Conclusion

- Providing nurses with education regarding the etiology, risk, classification, treatment and management of IAD statistically increased nurse knowledge
- The monthly HAPI rate is trending down and the NDNQI HAPIs remained below benchmark even with 62.5% of patients with an incontinent component

Limitations

- Small sample size reducing generalizability
- Short implementation period
- Minimal time before post-test

Recommendations

- Continue to collect monthly HAPI data
- Introduce IAD education hospital wide
- Make changes to annual HAPI education and protocol to include IAD
- Add IAD categories and treatment protocol to charting system

References

Monthly Hospital Acquired Pressure Injury Rate with Incontinence

Quarterly Prevalence Study Hospital Acquired Pressure Injury Rate with Incontinence

